

**Synopsis and Proposal for the thesis of
MTech (Research) in Information Science & Technology
Under
Srinivas University, Karnataka, India**

Title:

Computing & Information Sciences Domain at Private Universities in India:
A Knowledge Mapping with Trends, Emerging Scenario & Future
possibilities for creating a True Digital India

1. 0 Introduction & Statement of the Problem

Education is an important facet of development for man and society. Education, training, and research are an integral and integrated part each other and are responsible and dedicated for the better and healthy knowledge cultivation. Educational Institutions are responsible for dedication of knowledge activities such as collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination of knowledge and similar activities. India as a developing country grows faster to reach a status of developed nation. Education is a vital source and facet. Development of a country as a whole many a ways depends on the subjects and fields having applied in nature. Information Technology and Computing related subjects are playing a great part for the complete and modern development of society. Even education systems have changed with the integration and application of Information Technology. The growths of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) are rapid in recent past as far as India is concerned. The increasing numbers of institutions, universities, especially self-financed educational institutions are eye-catching. There are many merits and demerits of such type of institutions. Developing countries are moving towards better knowledge cultivation and development *countries such as China, Colombia, Malaysia, Mauritius, India, Brazil, South Africa etc.* are moving towards better knowledge dissemination and solid manpower development for all-round development. India is developing its social, economical strategies for better a world and thus there is an urgent need for the development of such programs related to the computing which are much applied and helps to reach knowledge economy. Many programs are available worldwide in different level such as Bachelors, Masters, and Doctoral Degrees which deals nature of such kind. However, India is also slowly designing educational programs. In the area of Computing, Computer Science was most earlier and available worldwide apart from the related merged domains few other areas have been generated in Information Spectrum viz. Information Technology, Information Systems, Informatics, Information Science etc. Though these are related but sometimes also differs the areas and coursework. India is seventh largest country and second most populated

country (1.2 billion) in the world. It is also a place for ancient Indus valley civilization. Irrespective of many constraints and challenges faced by the country before and after independence due to the issues of *Poverty, Corruption, and Dishonesty, Inadequate public healthcare systems, Financial Constraint* etc., India is now set to provide quality higher education to many of its aspirant youngsters. Consequently, India is now a home for more than 40,000 colleges in professional and technical areas offering Bachelors to Doctoral Programs in higher education. Though, universities are the highest level of educational institutions in the country established by the State Legislative Assembly or Parliament or UGC, there are about 90+ Institutions of National Importance (INI), which are super specialty institutions in diverse field such as Engineering, Management, Basic & Applied Science, Architecture, Pharmaceutical Sciences, Medical Sciences etc. These institutions are treated as important and greater value among the students as well as common people than even central universities due to the reason for their autonomy and financial status to make innovations and better quality education. Many of such institutions are also established and run by the Govt. of India viz. Bose Institute, Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics etc. (about 200+). A basic overview of Indian universities under four categories including Central Universities (5.7%), State universities (44.3%), Private universities (35%), and Deemed to be universities (15%).

In India Computing and Information related domains mainly concentrated with the nomenclatures of Computer Science, Computer Engineering, Computer Applications within Computing Segment. While in Information space the nomenclature Information Technology is only available. Though internationally within Information space many other domains are exists viz. Informatics, Information Science, Information Systems, Information Management, Information and Knowledge Management and so on.

Moreover Information Sciences are concentrated on various domains and as a result several new nomenclatures and fields have been generated with the promotion of interdisciplinary research. Among such fields few important are—

- Bio Information Science
- Health Information Science
- Geo Information Science
- Chemo Information Science
- Social Information Science
- Library Information Science
- Business Information Science
- Quantum Information Science etc.

Apart from these many other skill based areas within Information Technology also booming and among these few important are include—Usability Engineering, Human Computer Interaction, Cloud Computing, Big Data Systems etc.

Skills are very much important and valuable for the betterment of organizations, institutions, and individuals. Skills are important criteria for the work performance and employment. Universities and Higher Educational Institutions are moving towards introducing emerging programs and studies. Many universities in India as well are moving towards newer, emerging and skill-based domain and fields. Among the universities and HEIs private and deemed universities are doing well. Though State and Central Universities are working to consider such events but still not able to reach that height due to several issues. As far as initiative of private universities in India few emerging areas of Computing and Information Technologies in which academic programs have been started are include—

- Cloud Computing
- Big Data
- Mobile Based Applications
- Information and Cyber Security

This is also important move by the private universities regarding offering of domain specific Information Science programs viz. Bio Information Sciences—Health Information Science, Geo Information Science, Chemo Information Science, Social Information Science, Library Information Science, Business Information Science, Quantum Information Science etc. State and Central Universities are still rigid for many reasons and thus many private universities in India doing well in terms of offering of Small and broad nomenclatures within Information Technology and Computing programs/ fields. Hence offering subjects in multiple areas of Computing and Informatics, Skill based areas, domain specific IT and Information Sciences areas are the important initiative of the private universities and the current research work thus undertaken with the designated title '*Computing & Information Sciences Domain at Private Universities in India: A Knowledge Mapping with Trends, Emerging Scenario & Future possibilities for creating a True Digital India*' with a possible emphasis on education, future programs and policy formulation.

2.0 Benefits

The present work is conceptual and contextual in nature and deals with interdisciplinary in nature. Among the core benefits it will be helpful to learn the following—

- It is possible to know the actual characteristics of Computing and Information Sciences and such as how Computer Science, IST was formed. The main benefits of 'Information Sciences' particularly to the community or society.

- It will be helpful in drawing out the basic differences between Computer Science, Computer Application, IT and IST and judge the key value of Information Sciences for the professionals and academic field.
- Different areas and facets of Information Sciences including level of courses, degrees, institutions conducting these courses are possible to learn, and find out the possible programme for the future academic and interdisciplinary world.
- It will help in knowing the Higher Education Systems in India with reference to the Private Universities.
- The research would be beneficial as it will explore the current nomenclatures, degrees, programs etc are offered in the private universities.
- It will helpful to learn the status of skill based subjects, programs etc available in Indian private universities.
- It will help to know about the domain specific Information Science and its availability in Indian academia in isolated manner.
- It will help to learn about the emerging programs among the private universities in Computer Applications with special reference to the possible skill based programs, domain specific programs.
- It will help to learn about the emerging programs among the private universities in Engineering Degrees in specialization format with special reference to the possible skill based programs, domain specific programs
- It will help to draw a picture of research degrees specifically in the field of IT and Computing in India with reference to the Private Universities.
- The study will help to learn about the collaborated, industry integrated programs started in Private universities leading to the fields of IT and Computing.
- The study will be beneficial to know about the Lateral Entry Scheme in Indian Private Universities leading to the fields of Computer Science, Computer Applications.
- It will help to learn about the Multiple Duration based Computing/ CA programs in Indian Private Universities.
- It will helpful to learn about the changing flexibility in IT and Computing related programs and subjects offered in Private Universities.
- India is moving towards more digitally equipped and IT associated nation and in this regard newer subjects, programs and solid and ready manpower etc are highly solicited. Thus research work would help in this regard as well.

As a whole the proposed work will be helpful not only for learning the current trends, programs, nomenclatures in Private Universities but also helpful in fixing future trend, possibilities and potentialities (please refer Fig: 1).

Fig: 1-Benefits of Proposed Research Work

3.0 Objective and Proposed Methods

The main aim and objective of this research work is include gather basics of Education and Training in India in Private University segment with reference to whole Computing and Information related programs in different levels. It is a basic and theoretical cum interdisciplinary work and thus associated with the policy affairs. Some of the core agenda of this research work are includes (but not limited to)—

- To learn about Education Systems in India from past to modern age including types of educational institutes and their focus.
- To learn about the role of educational systems that leads Information Technology and Computing industry in India.
- To learn about the Information Technology and Computing fields in India compare to other parts of the globe.

- To dig out the current strength of technical, management education in India including available degrees in different perspectives.
- To learn about the differences between Computer Science, Computer Application, IT and IST and judge the key value of Information Sciences for the professionals and academic field.
- To dig out the the Higher Education Systems in India with reference to the Private Universities and also the research would be beneficial as it will explore the current nomenclatures, degrees, programs etc are offered in the private universities
- To learn about the industry integrated programs started in Private universities leading to the fields of IT and Computing and also to know about the Lateral Entry Scheme in Indian Private Universities leading to MCA degrees including the Multiple Duration based Computing/ CA programs in Indian Private Universities.
- To dig out the changing flexibility in IT and Computing related programs and subjects offered in Private Universities including new domain focused programs etc.

Fig: 2The Methodologies and strategies of the research designing for ultimate scope and periphery.

The present study is conceptual and interdisciplinary in nature, its aim has been depicted in Fig: 2. The present work is deals with educational aspects and affairs to learn about the Education Systems in India, the current strength of technical, management education in India and also educational regulatory. The focus of the research work is Information and Computing related

education systems mapping in India with reference to the Private Universities. Hence for doing the research work mixed mode of methodologies have been adopted. Review of literature plays a vital role to dig out questions that are proposed in this work. Moreover few other affairs such as web survey also been carried out in respective websites such as UGC, AITCE, PCI, BCI, MCI, DCI, ICMR etc. Moreover to find out and show few best universities in modern India, the NIRF ranking also been used. As the work is dedicated to the private universities in India so that the core link used: <https://www.ugc.ac.in/privatuniversity.aspx> for reaching pan India basis private universities and their programs in the field of Computer and Information Sciences.

The present work is proposed chapter wise composition and here each Chapter has been planned with published research work with introductory chapter information and guidance. There are total nine (9) chapters have been planned for. Details of chapters and possible publication titles are depicted in the section Thesis formation and Chapterization.

4.0 Language, Communication and Tools

Research and innovation is internationally mainly carried in English language and as a result English is treated as communicative language of this proposed work. However few other languages (including but not limited to the) Hindi, Bengali. The thesis is proposed to prepare in English language. Apart from use of conventional tools few other emerging tools and technologies such as Computers, CD-DVD, Document processing systems such as PDF, Database systems, cloud database are essential for this work. Moreover internet as well as E-Mail including machine such as fax, pager, telephone and mobile phones are also need to use for fruitful output of the study. Questionnaire and survey methods (in few cases also planned for) are also important tool in this research work. Software and computing applications, indexing database, these database are required to study properly. Various kinds of statistical techniques and simple spreadsheets are to be used for representing data with the form of pie, histogram, bar diagram for healthy analysis and representation of the data.

5.0 Thesis Formation and Chapterization

The present for entitled '*Computing & Information Sciences Domain at Private Universities in India: A Knowledge Mapping with Trends, Emerging Scenario & Future possibilities for creating a True Digital India*' is purely interdisciplinary in nature and as far as this work the possible publications are yet to composite in the thesis for the MTech (Research) chapter-wise. Here total nine (9) active chapters are proposed with another for annexure.

Chapter: 1

Introduction, Objective & Methodologies Adopted

1.0 Introduction & Statement of the Problem

1.1 Benefits

Research Proposal Submitted by P.K. Paul for the MTech (Research) in IST

- 1.2 Objective and Methods Adopted
- 1.3 Language, Communication and Tools
- 1.4 Thesis Formation and Chapterization
- 1.5 Major Work Undertaken and Incorporated
- 1.6 Conclusion

Chapter: 2

Indian Higher Education, Computing Programs: Trends & Potentialities (Based on Publications)

2.0 Overview

- 2.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter
- 2.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- Indian Higher Education: *With Slant to Information Technology*— A Fundamental Overview
- Computing & Information Related Degrees worldwide & India—*An Analytical Policy Research*
- Computing & Allied Engineering Domain in India with reference to Private Universities: *A Case Study of Bachelors Programs*
- Computing & Allied Engineering Domain in India with reference to Private Universities: *A Case Study of Masters Programs*
- Emerging Degrees and Collaboration: The Context of Engineering Sciences in Computing & IT—*An Analysis for Enhanced Policy Formulation in India*

2.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 3

Bachelors & Masters Computing Programs into New Directions (Based on Publications)

3.0 Overview

- 3.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

3.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- Bachelors Degree in Computing and allied fields in India Emphasizing Private Universities—*A Study of Science Platform (BCA & BSc)*
- Bachelor of Computer Applications (BCA): *An Applied Science Program into a new Direction?*
- MCA Degree Beyond traditional Mathematical & Logical Prerequisite & Concentration: *Is it into a new Direction?*
- MSc with emerging Specializations and Hons/Major: *A Case of IT & Computing Fields in Indian Private Universities*

3.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 4

Computing & Increasing Domain based Information Sciences (Based on Publications)

4.0 Overview

4.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

4.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- The increasing trend of Domain based Information Sciences programs in India—*An Investigation of Private Universities*
- Bio Informatics in private universities in India: *An Emerging Study on promotion of Biological Information Sciences*
- Informatics as a branch in Indian Academics with case of private universities: *emphasizing Biological Information Sciences*
- Health Information Science and its growing popularities in Indian self financed universities: *Emphasizing Private Universities—A Study*

4.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 5

Changing policies and flexibilities in Computing & Information Sciences in India (Based on Publications)

5.0 Overview

5.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

Research Proposal Submitted by P.K. Paul for the MTech (Research) in IST

5.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- Computing and Information Sciences with changing entry criteria from Non Mathematical Sciences: International Trends and its adoption in Indian Private Universities—*Study of BCA Program*
- BSc in Computing and IT related subjects with flexible and changing entry criteria: International Trends and adoption in Indian Private Universities—*A Knowledge Survey*
- Computing & Information Science Degrees with emerging flexibilities and entry level criteria: Study of MSc Programs in IT and Computing Fields in Indian Private Universities

5.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 6

Lateral Entry, Top Ups and Alternative to Computing and Informatics Programs (Based on Publications)

6.0 Overview

6.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

6.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- MCA Degree in 1 to 5 Year!—*An Investigation of Private Universities in India*
- MCA Program and Lateral Entry Opportunities in India: *A Study of Private Universities*
- Growing popularity of Post Graduate Diploma programs in IT and Computing in Indian Private Universities: *An Overview*
- PGDCA and other allied Post Graduate Diploma programs importance in Masters Entry in India: *A New Horizon for the Bachelor holders from Diverse Fields*

6.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 7

New Age Specializations and Domain Concentration in Computing and Informatics Programs in Private Universities (Based on Publications)

7.0 Overview

7.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

7.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

Research Proposal Submitted by P.K. Paul for the MTech (Research) in IST

- Computing Academics into New Age Applied Science Programs and Fields Emphasizing Trend on Animation and Multimedia Technology—*An Investigation of Indian Private Universities*
- Computing Academics into New Age Programs and Fields: Big Data Analytics & Data Sciences in Indian Academics—*An Academic Investigation*
- Is Indian Computing academic units are interested in the areas of IT? *A Case of Cloud Computing & Virtualization*
- *Business Information Sciences* emphasizing Digital Marketing as an emerging field of Business & IT: A Study of Indian Private Universities
- Role of Economics and Allied Sciences into Information and Computing fields: Emphasizing Economics & IT Programs—*World and Indian Context*

7.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 8

Research Programs in Computing and Informatics Programs (Based on Publications)

8.0 Overview

8.1 Introduction & Guide to Chapter

8.2 Outcome and Findings as Publications

- MPhil as Masters by Research Work Programs in IT & Computing Fields: *A Case Study of Indian Private Universities*
- MPhil as Masters by Research Work Programs in IT & Computing Fields: *A Case Study of Indian Private Universities*
- Doctoral Programs in Computing and allied subjects in India with Reference to Private Universities: *A Growing Trend*

8.3 Suggestion with Concluding Remarks

Chapter: 9

Suggestion & Conclusion

Chapter: 10

Annexure

6.0 Conclusion

Education is the key element for development. Universities and educational institutions are growing rapidly in India. During 1970-1990, India received a good number of government institutions and universities. Many bodies have been developed in nation to control education systems of various fields including professional subjects and areas. Among other subjects Information Technology is playing a great role for the development of education systems. Information Science and Computing is a diverse field and gaining rapidly around the world. Educational institutes are offering several programs in Computing & IT. The enrolment of general education as well as professional education is excelled in recent past with the introduction of different subjects and many super specialty institutions viz. IITs, NITs, IIMs and so on. But still it is fact that Information Sciences stream not yet flourish welled and thus many private universities are doing well for starring new age programs, new subjects, micro and skill based subjects etc. As far as level of education is concerned Information and Computing is vast one in the field of knowledge. The present work will be worthy to know the current status of promoting this field by the private universities and also for the better policy formulation of state and central governments, institutions and coming organizations etc.

(Prantosh Kumar Paul)
Signature of the Applicant/ Scholar

